

Polarography of Molybdenum (VI) at D.M.E. in Different Organic Acids Media

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Polarographic behaviour of Mo (VI) at d. m. e. employing different organic acids, mandelic acid, succinic acid, and formic acid-sod. formate as supporting electrolytes has been studied. The effects of variation of Hg-pressure, concentration and pH on the waves have been investigated. In 0.1M mandelic acid medium Mo(VI) produces two waves with $E_{1/2}$ -0.26v. and -0.63 v. (vs. SCE), the total height of which was found to vary linearly with Mo(VI) concentration. In succinic acid and formic acid-sod. formate media, an irreversible wave with half wave potentials about 0.51v. and -48v. respectively was obtained, the height of which in each case does not show proportionality with Mo(VI) concentration. The values of $\frac{1}{2} id/hk_{app}$ at different Hg-pressures in all cases show constancy and suggest the occurrence of diffusion controlled waves. The reduction wave in mandelic acid medium appeared to be of analytical importance and hence the effects of the presence of various elements viz. W, Fe (III), V, Mn, Cr, Ti(III), Uo^{++} , Te, and camphor on the wave have also been studied.

The literature on the polarographic behaviour of Mo(VI) in media composed of organic acids is scanty. The available references are of Deford & Co-workers¹, R. Pribil & A. Blazek², L. Meites³, E. P. Parry & M. G. Yakubik⁴, and John W. Grenier & L. Meites⁵. No reference has been found regarding the polarographic study of Mo(VI) in mandelic acid, succinic acid, and formic acid-sodium formate media. The present investigation has, therefore, been undertaken with a view to study the polarography of Mo(VI) in above mentioned media and to determine suitable conditions for the determination of molybdenum (VI) in presence of various elements.

Anal.R. (BDH) reagents, mandelic acid, succinic acid, formic acid, sodium formate, sodium molybdate, thymol were used and their solutions prepared in air-free conductivity water.

EXPERIMENTAL

A manual polarograph with Scalamp galvanometer as current recorder was used for the entire polarographic work. A dropping mercury electrode having the following characteristics, $m=2.416$ mg./sec. $t=3.58$ secs., and $m^{2/3}t^{1/6}=2.220$ $mg^{2/3}sec^{-1/6}$ (at -1.0v. in 0.1MKNO₃) was used in conjunction with calomel electrode connected to the cell by low resistance salt bridge. The cell solution was deaerated by bubbling purified hydrogen for 10-15 minutes and was kept immersed in an electrically maintained thermostat at constant temperature $22 \pm 0.1^\circ$. A glass electrode of the range 0-8 pH and Cambridge null deflection type pH-meter was used for pH measurements.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Polarography of Mo(VI) in mandelic acid medium: Using 0.1M mandelic acid (pH 1.16) as supporting electrolyte and 0.005% thymol as maximum suppressor the polarographic behaviour of Mo(VI) has been investigated. In this medium Mo(VI) reduced at d.m.e. producing two waves with half wave potentials about -0.26v. and -0.63v. (vs. SCE). Both the waves are well defined and irreversible. The height of the first wave (fig. 1, curve-I) is found to be approximately one half of the second wave indicating that the Mo(VI) is probably reduced first to +5 state and then to +3 state. The final rising portion of the wave at about -1.3v. shows the discharge of hydrogen. No constant diffusion current region is reached for the first wave, and for the second wave, a well defined limiting current plateau, almost horizontal, is obtained upto the considerably wider range of potential. At higher pH levels (pH 3 or >3), it is found that total height of wave decreases, the $E_{1/2}$ shifts to more negative side and on increasing potential beyond 0.3v an appreciable decrease in wave height is observed upto 1.0v. after which current increases sharply (fig. 1).

This is not a regular maximum, the presence of thymol even in higher concentration (0.1%) has no effect. The decrease may be attributed to the desorption of the reducible species on the d.m.e. at negative potentials. To get rid of these minima the effect of camphor on the wave was also investigated. In presence of higher concentrations of camphor (0.1%) the total height of the wave decreases and minima disappears, beyond the minima, camphor itself begins to be desorbed and the adsorption and subsequent reduction of molybdate again occur so that the current gradually increases upto the value it would be in the absence of camphor.

A series of polarograms of solutions containing different concentrations of Mo(VI) in presence of 0.1M mandelic acid and 0.005% thymol have been recorded. The diffusion current value at each concentration was determined and the values of " i_d/C " and "I" (diffusion current constant) were calculated and tabulated below:

TABLE I

Test for the linearity of wave height with Mo(VI) concn. in mandelic acid medium.

Concn. of Mo (VI) mM/lit.	i_d after corr. for i_r (μ a)	i_d/C	$I = i_d/Cm^{2/3} t^{1/6}$
2.000	11.120	5.560	2.918
1.334	7.380	5.532	2.904
1.000	5.560	5.560	2.918
0.500	2.760	5.520	2.900
0.250	1.390	5.560	2.918
0.100	0.550	5.500	2.890

The plot of " i_d " vs. "C" yielded a straight line passing through the origin (fig. 2, curve-I) and values of " i_d/C " and "I" are found to be constant (table-I) which reveals that the total height of the wave is proportional to the concentration of Mo(VI).

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on reduction of 1.667 mM sodium molybdate in mandelic medium. (I) 0.1M mandelic acid, pH 2.15; (II) 0.1M mandelic acid+0.02M sodium mandelate, pH 2.60, and (III) 0.1M mandelic acid+0.04M sodium mandelate, pH 3.20.

Fig. 2. Plots of " i_d " vs. " c " in mandelic acid (I); formic acid-sodium formate (II), and succinic acid (III) media.

Polarograms of Mo(VI) at different heights of Hg-column have also been drawn, the values of " $i_d h^{1/2} \text{ eff}$ " have been calculated which were found to be constant. The height of the wave was found to be directly proportional to the square root of the pressure on the d.m.e. (fig. 3, curve-I), indicating that the reduction process is diffusion controlled.

Polarography of Mo(VI) in formic acid-sod. formate medium: In presence of 0.1M formic acid—0.04M sodium formate (pH 3.25) and 0.005% thymol Mo(VI) yields a single step irreversible wave with $E_{1/2}$ about -0.48v. (vs. SCE) (fig. 4—curve-I). The variation in pH of the medium causes considerable changes in wave characteristics. At lower pH(2.75) Mo(VI) in this medium produced an ill defined flat wave and at higher pH(4.1) a wave with considerably decreased height and increased $E_{1/2}$ (Fig. 4, curves-II & III).

The limiting current after correction for residual current does not show proportionality with Mo(VI) concentration (fig. 4, curve-II). The diffusion current constant (" I ") is found to increase with the increase in Mo(VI) concentration (table-II). This may be due to an increasing degree of polymerisation of the predominating molybdate species with increasing concentration.

TABLE II

Test for the linearity of wave height with Mo(VI) concn. in 0.1M formic acid-0.4M sod. formate:

Concn. of Mo (VI) mM/lit.	i_d after corr. for i_r (μA)	i_d/C	$I = i_d/Cm^{2/3} t^{1/6}$
2.000	5.900	2.950	1.559
1.000	2.100	2.100	1.163
0.667	1.275	1.911	1.010
0.500	0.875	1.750	0.925
0.200	0.244	1.220	0.645

The effect of the variation of Hg-pressure on the height of wave produced by Mo(VI) in formic acid-sod. formate medium has also been studied. Plot of " i_d ", determined at different heights of Hg-column, vs. $h_{eff}^{1/2}$ yield a straight line indicating that the height of the wave is diffusion controlled (fig. 3, curve-II).

Fig. 3. Plots of " i_d " vs. " $h_{eff}^{1/2}$ " in mandelic acid(I); formic acid-sodium formate (II), and succinic acid (III) media.

Fig 4. Polarograms of M/500 sodium molybdate in formic acid-sod. formate at different pH levels. (I) 0.1M formic acid, pH 2.75; (II) 0.1M formic acid -0.04M sodium formate; pH 3.25; and (III) 0.1M formic acid -0.1M. sodium formate, pH, 4,10.

Polarography of Mo(VI) in succinic acid medium: In medium composed of 0.1M succinic acid and 0.005% thymol, the polarographic behaviour of Mo(VI) is almost similar to that in formic acid-sod. formate medium. Mo(VI) is reduced in this medium producing an irreversible single step polarogram having $E_{1/2}$ about -0.51v. In this case also " i_d " does not show linear relationship with Mo(VI) concentration but varies linearly with the square root of the height of Hg-column (fig. 3, curve-III). At higher pH value ill defined waves were obtained (fig. 5, curves-I, II & III).

TABLE III

Test for the linearity of i_d with Mo(VI) concn. in 0.1M succinic acid:

Concn. of Mo (VI) mM/lit.	i_d after corr. for i_r (μa)	i_d/C	$I = i_d/Cm^{2/3} t^{1/6}$
2.000	7.573	3.786	1.974
1.354	4.995	3.296	1.718
1.000	3.190	3.190	1.663
0.500	1.395	3.790	1.456
0.200	0.530	2.650	1.380
0.100	0.244	2.440	1.372

The reduction wave obtained in mandelic acid medium has been found to be of analytical importance as the magnitude of " i_d " strictly depends on the Mo(VI) concentration. The effect of the presence of various cations on Mo(VI) wave in mandelic acid medium

have been studied together with the role of camphor in masking the interfering waves. The elements, viz. Ni, Co, W, Fe (III), Mn, Cr, Te, in presence of 0.1% camphor do not interfere. Molybdenum(VI) in small amounts can be determined in presence of above mentioned cations. The detail study concerning with the polarographic determination of Mo(VI) by electrochemical masking technique is in progress.

Fig. 5. Polarograms of 1.334 mM sodium molybdate in succinic acid medium at different pH levels. (I) 0.1M succinic acid, pH 2.84; (II) 0.1M succinic acid-0.025M sodium succinate, pH 3.89; and (III) 0.1M succinic acid-0.1M sodium succinate, pH 4.70.

The polarographic behaviour of Mo(VI) in salicylic and sulphosalicylic acids media have also been investigated. Mo(VI) gives ill defined waves in both the media and hence a detailed study could not be made.

It is apparent that Mo(VI) produces a well defined irreversible double wave polarogram in mandelic acid medium, the total height of which varies linearly with the concentration of Mo(VI); the wave can be successfully utilised for the determination of Mo(VI) in presence of various other elements. When formic acid-sodium formate and succinic acid were used as supporting electrolytes, Mo(VI) produced diffusion controlled waves the height of which in each case does not show strict proportionality with Mo(VI) concentration.

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